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Media ensembles in depopulating municipalities and news deserts: insights from Castilla-La Mancha, Spain

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzes the role of media ensembles in municipalities at risk of depopulation in Castilla-La Mancha, Spain, exploring their function as communicative resilience resources in areas classified as news deserts. It seeks to move beyond the traditional focus on the absence of conventional media by adopting a processual perspective that acknowledges the interaction among various communication channels and practices at the local level. A quantitative approach was used, including the construction of a database with information on 721 municipalities concerning the presence of institutional and non-professional communication channels. Descriptive and inferential statistical analyses were conducted, complemented by geographic analysis tools to identify spatial patterns in the distribution of these resources. The findings show that, although smaller municipalities tend to have fewer communication channels, some exceptions exhibit high communicative activity, demonstrating resilience dynamics. Geographic analysis revealed territorial concentration patterns in media ensembles, suggesting processes of influence and transmission among neighboring municipalities. The study concludes that research on depopulated areas should move beyond assessing the mere absence of conventional media to consider the diversity of infrastructures and practices that sustain the circulation of information. As a novel contribution, the research proposes the integration of geographic analysis into local communication studies, offering a comprehensive perspective that deepens our understanding of the dynamics of media ensembles in depopulating contexts.

1. Introduction

Policies addressing the demographic challenge of depopulation have become a strategic priority in Spain, a country marked by vast rural areas, significant territorial imbalances, and an estimated 50 % of municipalities at risk of disappearing in the coming decades (Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y Reto demográfico, 2021). Since the creation of the Commissioner for the Demographic Challenge in 2017, the issue has gained increasing political relevance, eventually acquiring ministerial status. In recent years, both public administrations and citizen movements have sought to confront the consequences of this phenomenon across its many dimensions.

This article aligns with that scientific and political framework by focusing on digital communication as a key dimension—not only for diagnosing what is happening in depopulated territories but also for shaping policies aimed at social and territorial cohesion (Molina Ibáñez et al., 2023). We argue that digital media are essential tools for ensuring

the circulation of local information and for contributing to the symbolic construction of territorial belonging—that is, to the inscription and visibility of a territorially grounded “we”.

Moving beyond methodological approaches centered on media structures, the mediatization paradigm (Krotz, 2007) invites us to examine how media logics—both in the present and through a longitudinal historical lens—have reshaped societies by making their institutions increasingly dependent on the media sphere. As a macroconcept, mediatization requires applied, context-sensitive studies to grasp how this process unfolds in specific social domains and territories. Due to an urban bias in communication research (Zerrer, 2024), relatively little attention has been paid to how mediatization operates in rural geographies (Zerrer et al., 2022). This article contributes to filling that gap by analyzing the communicative resources of a depopulated Spanish region that includes large areas classified as news deserts (Saiz Echezarreta, Galletero-Campos, & Arias Molineros, 2023).

We thus propose a case study of Castilla-La Mancha, a region

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particularly affected by depopulation: 80 % of its municipalities have fewer than 2000 inhabitants, and 58 % have a population density below 8 people/km^{1,2}. This situation has prompted the development of a cross-cutting policy approach that has been recognized as a European benchmark (Gobierno de Castilla-La Mancha, 2025). The pioneering Law February 2021 on Economic, Social, and Tax Measures to Address Depopulation and Promote Rural Development in Castilla-La Mancha explicitly calls for territorial communication strategies—an idea this paper seeks to explore further. To that end, we present a methodological proposal aimed at advancing the analysis of the concept of *media ensembles*, which will be developed theoretically in the following sections.

1.1. News deserts

For over a decade, the media industry has faced a structural crisis in its business model, driven by digitalization, the widespread availability of free content, and the emergence of new tech actors dominating the content distribution market (Trappel & Tomaz, 2021). Local media—typically small, independent outlets—have borne the brunt of this crisis, grappling with economic sustainability in limited markets, reduced staffing, and challenges in implementing innovation (Nielsen, 2015). The closure and downsizing of these outlets have led to a reduction in local news provision, sparking interest among scholars (Rodríguez-Urra et al., 2024) and giving rise to the concept of *news deserts* in the U.S. These are defined as “a community lacking fresh, daily local news and information” (Ferrier, 2016, p. 1); “a geographic area with few or no news outlets and limited coverage” (Usher, 2015); or “a community, either rural or urban, where residents have very limited access to the sort of credible and comprehensive news and information that feed democracy at the grassroots level” (Abernathy, 2020, p. 18). While there is no single definition, the concept clearly links geography to the availability, access, and use of quality local news, as well as the critical information needs of communities (Gulyas et al., 2023), although it is closely linked to the structure of local printed newspapers.

Early U.S.-based projects—*The Media Deserts Project Monitoring* and *Expanding News Deserts*—focused on geolocating local newspapers, an approach that has inspired similar mapping efforts elsewhere. National-scale reports have been produced in countries such as Argentina (FOPEA, 2021), Colombia (FLIP, 2016), Brazil (Atlas da Notícia, 2022), and Portugal (Jerónimo et al., 2022). In Europe, the *Local Media for Democracy* project has assessed the 27 EU member states using indicators that go beyond merely counting media outlets. These include economic and political conditions, the safety of local journalists and minority groups, and the capacity for audience engagement (Verza et al., 2024).

This growing body of research confirms that, while the concept of news deserts has international relevance, its application across diverse contexts reveals key limitations. In Europe, for instance, there is a strong tradition of public service media (Arriaza Ibarra et al., 2015), in contrast to the U.S. model, which relies more heavily on market-driven local news—potentially slowing the spread of news deserts (Kermer et al.,

2024). Large-scale comparative models often fail to capture the communicative dynamics of places without local media, overlooking the heterogeneity of subnational areas and their specific influences on the media ecosystem. Factors such as demographic patterns and population density (Negreira-Rey, Vázquez-Herrero, & López-García, 2023; Sainz-Echezarreta et al., 2023) affect local media sustainability, and rural, remote areas are especially vulnerable to becoming news deserts (Qin, 2024; Usher, 2021). Furthermore, many of these studies have focused exclusively on print newspapers, neglecting other relevant sources of local information such as hyperlocal digital platforms. However, the latest *Digital News Report 2025* (Newman et al., 2024) has reaffirmed the reliance on social media platforms for news consumption, including private messaging apps with 15 % reported using WhatsApp as a source for news in the last week and 26 % using Facebook (p.15). In Spain, the focus of this study, social networks have consolidated their position as the second most common source of information (46 %) (Sierra et al., 2025, p. 14) and Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube and Instagram stand out in the top positions, the first two with a reach of a quarter of the population.

These limitations point to the need for more detailed and context-sensitive research on spatial inequalities in local journalism and in the availability and access to local news, as well as on the factors that shape these disparities (Gulyas, 2021). This calls for methodological approaches that go beyond geolocating media outlets and include case studies to illuminate the specific challenges faced by these territories. Recent studies have taken steps in this direction, focusing on small municipalities such as Manteigas, Portugal (2900 inhabitants; Torre et al., 2024), Lightning Ridge, Australia (2284; Magasic et al., 2023), and Baldwin City, USA (4627; Smethers et al., 2021). These works investigate local information habits and the impact of lacking a professional news outlet. They converge on findings such as weakened social fabric, reduced space for institutional scrutiny, increased susceptibility to misinformation, and diminished emotional connection among community members (Mathews, 2022). Moreover, residents often must take an active role in seeking information via websites and social media, a task that demands both technological skills and digital literacy.

We start from the premise that areas labeled as news deserts are not necessarily devoid of information, nor are they always perceived as such by residents (Collier & Graham, 2022). In the absence of professional media, local news often circulates through a patchwork of resources, frequently linked to local institutions—signs of what Usher (2021) calls *communicative resilience*. From this perspective, the concept of *news oases*, proposed by Wang (2023), is especially relevant: geographically defined areas where local news distribution remains relatively healthy. However, in this study we explore that notion not through the lens of legacy media—largely absent in our case region, where there are only 17 professional local media outlets in areas categorized as depopulated—but through the concept of *media ensembles*: the set of (mostly digital) communicative resources and practices that characterize a particular social domain (Hasebrink & Hepp, 2017). In this case, that domain is formed by territorially grounded communities that share patterns of demographic decline (Pinilla & Sáez, 2021).

In sum, for the purposes of this study we adopt a contextualized definition of news deserts as *municipalities or clusters of municipalities where residents have very limited access to professional locally produced, regularly updated, and credible news outlets, particularly those able to meet basic information needs for community life and democratic participation* (Ferrier, 2014; Usher, 2015; Abernathy, 2020; Gulyas et al., 2023). In the Spanish context, such situations tend to emerge in rural areas undergoing sustained demographic decline, such as Castilla-La Mancha. Following Law February 2021 of Castilla-La Mancha (Arts. 10–11), we understand a rural municipality not only in terms of population size and density, but also through broader indicators such as demographic evolution and aging, employment structure, land use, and accessibility to urban centers. The law distinguishes four categories of rural zones

¹ According to this approach, it is preferable to conceive of media as processes, involving changes in materiality, infrastructure, and modes of institutionalization (values, routines, practices) (Hepp, 2020, pp. 56–99). Moreover, understanding media as processes allows for an expanded notion of communication media—beyond conventional news outlets—to include amateur publications, festival booklets, or even the bar as a communicative device.

² Although each individual media ensemble component was coded as a binary indicator, the overall index (ranging from 0 to 5) represents an aggregated measure that approximates an interval scale. This approach assumes that each additional channel contributes equivalently to the municipality’s communication capacity, thus justifying the use of parametric methods such as linear regression. Similar practices are common in social sciences—for instance, when summing Likert-scale items—where aggregated scores are treated as continuous variables (see Carifio & Perla, 2007 for further discussion).

—sparsely populated, at risk of depopulation, intermediate rural, and peri-urban rural— and allows their application both to single municipalities and to clusters of contiguous municipalities. In this study, we focus primarily on the categories of *sparsely populated* and *at risk of depopulation*, which best capture the dynamics of demographic decline and communicative vulnerability under examination.

1.2. Objectives

Drawing on the perspective of *communication geography*—which emphasizes how geographic and demographic factors shape communicative dynamics (Fast & Abend, 2022; Jansson & Ritter, 2024)—this research sets out to.

- Map the digital communicative resources (*media ensembles*) present in the lowest-density areas of Castilla-La Mancha, most of which are categorized as news deserts.
- Identify possible geographic or demographic patterns in the distribution of digital media ensembles in the region, with a special focus on communities with higher levels of communicative activity.
- Assess methodological approaches to the study of news deserts by analyzing the factors that determine the presence or absence of communicative resources in these territories.

2. Theoretical framework

2.1. The notion of media ensembles

This study forms part of a broader research project exploring how collective media use and appropriation shape local community building in depopulated areas. The mediatization paradigm holds that our everyday practices are mediatized (Hepp, 2020), as we rely on a range of media and technologies on a daily basis that transform our experiences, including those related to the search for and consumption of information. We understand media as both communicative tools and spaces that enable the emergence, stabilization, and transformation of territorial identities. If we understand the local community as a communicative figuration, it must be analyzed from a transmedia perspective (Schróder, 2018) that encompasses not only the availability and consumption of legacy media but also, in a complementary way, the use of a wide range of devices, platforms, and channels, engaging in diverse media practices as part of everyday life. This perspective, linked to a “non-media centric” media research, implies not studying a medium in isolation but also considering its position in the overall media “environment” or “configuration” of various media (Hepp, 2014). According to Hepp and Sinner (2025), within media and communication research focusing on community, the study of polymedia environments plays a central role.

Transmedia practices not only blur the uses of infrastructures and devices, intertwining the online and the offline, the public and the private, and the personal and professional communication (Coudry & Hepp, 2017; Deuze, 2012). Thus, local information does not circulate through a single channel but across multiple media simultaneously. However, for these channels to support social cohesion, generalized access, affordability, and media literacy among community members are essential (Madianou & Miller, 2013, p. 175, as cited by Hepp & Sinner, 2025). One of the defining traits of a community is the existence and use of a distinctive set of media (Hepp & Hasebrink, 2018, pp. 5–50). Community bonds remain stable across successive media generations. That is, the role of information circulation in fostering cohesion persists even as media shift—from printed newspapers to digital radio, social media, and mobile apps (Hepp, 2020). The notion of media ensembles—an intermediate concept between the media ecosystem, understood at the global level, and the media repertoire, focused on individual practices—designates clusters of media and communicative practices that operate simultaneously or sequentially within specific social

domains (organizations, communities, policy fields, in this case, depopulated rural municipalities) to shape everyday experience (Hasebrink & Hepp, 2017). A media ensemble involves not just the available channels, but also the dynamic, collective practices of adoption, combination, and use of media based on local contexts. In line with communication geography, geographic, political, and sociocultural conditions play a key role in determining how digital media are combined and used across a given territory.

Viewing local communication channels as media ensembles allows us to highlight their processual and heterogeneous nature. Rather than treating them as isolated tools for information dissemination, we emphasize their embeddedness in social processes (Deuze, 2012) Media ensembles both adapt to territorial conditions and actively shape, sustain, and transform local communities over time. Their configuration is never fixed: elements may enter, exit, or shift in relevance, function, and symbolic value. Changes in media use—across platforms, networks, and devices— alongside shifts in public communication policies, lead to reconfigurations. For example, the centrality of websites may give way to mobile apps or social networks, which themselves evolve, replace, or complement each other. In the context of news circulation, the crisis of commercial journalism—or the persistence of news deserts— often involves the disappearance of local news outlets and the growing prominence of alternative media in local ensembles, such as community radio stations, grassroots publications, or platforms like Facebook.

Media ensembles are composed of material elements (infrastructure, technologies) and discursive practices that, over time, may reach temporary stabilization or institutionalization. These configurations, however, remain open to transformation, with new platforms, networks, or devices being integrated into the ensemble. We choose to work with the notion of media ensembles because it expands the conceptual framework of news deserts in several key ways: (1) it shifts the focus from scarcity of legacy media to the resources enabling communicative resilience and information dissemination; (2) it includes not only professional media but also their intersections with municipal, community, and amateur outlets; (3) it enables the development of media activity indicators comparable to those in fields like transport, health, or education—commonly used in geography and economics.

2.2. The role of municipal communication

For Moragas (2015), the concept of proximity communication brings together two fundamental dimensions of local journalism: the notion of territory and identity, and the closeness between senders and their audiences. However, the scholar had already warned ten years ago that in the near future a significant part of proximity communication would likely take place outside conventional media, constructing “a new ecology of communication” (p. 32). Whereas in the past local communication was limited to local newspapers and radio and television stations, today local information circulates across a variety of channels and devices within a much more complex ecosystem (Nygren, 2019). As Hermida (2016) states, news is always part of people’s social media feed, users encounter them while interacting with others, entertaining themselves, or browsing for new posts.

Some studies have thoroughly reviewed hyperlocal journalism initiatives in Spain (Negreira-Rey et al., 2020), but that is not the focus of this study. We map here those spaces, channels, and platforms through which local information circulates outside professional journalistic initiatives: on the one hand, the resources used by municipalities to disseminate local news within their communities, and on the other, amateur initiatives such as blogs, cultural magazines, or association publications.

Municipal communication is a tool for promoting civic participation, as established in Law July 1985 on the Bases of Local Government (Art. 69). In 2003, the Autonomous University of Barcelona developed a *Decalogue of Best Practices for Local Public Communication* (Moreno-Sardá et al., 2013), aimed primarily at publicly owned local media—print,

radio, TV, municipal and citizen websites— but applicable to all communication channels made possible by the digital ecosystem. These practices emphasize not only transparency, plurality, and information on municipal management, but also the need to “build a sense of community,” foster local identity, become “an informative reference point for citizens,” “spark interest,” and “promote civic and associative life.”

Local administrations thus play a crucial role in fostering communicative vitality within communities, and in recent years many have worked to embrace digital communication (López Alonso & Moreno López, 2019), with varying levels of success depending on available resources.

Most studies on the use of digital media in municipal communication have focused on provincial capitals and large cities (Bonsón, Royo & Cambra, 2018), leaving small municipalities largely unexamined. This study draws on the research by López Alonso and Moreno López (2019), which analyzed the use of social media in rural municipalities (under 10,000 inhabitants) across Spain. Their findings confirm that Facebook is by far the most used tool (93.04 % adoption), while less than half use other platforms: 52.47 % deploy mobile apps and 38.61 % use WhatsApp groups. The least used medium is the website: only 23.14 % maintain an active blog for news dissemination. As will be shown later, these trends align with some of the findings of this case study.

3. Methodology

This study applies a quantitative methodology using statistical and geospatial analysis techniques, combining mapping, descriptive and inferential statistical analysis through multiple regression models, and geospatial analysis with GIS tools and map visualization.

3.1. Sample

Castilla-La Mancha comprises 919 municipalities distributed unevenly across five provinces. Cuenca and Guadalajara, the northernmost provinces, account for 25.8 % and 31.3 % of the region’s municipalities, respectively. Most of these municipalities have fewer than 500 inhabitants. In contrast, the southern provinces—Albacete, Ciudad Real, and Toledo (the regional capital)—concentrate larger and more socio-economically dynamic municipalities.

This study includes 721 municipalities (78 % of the region’s total), covering all areas classified as at risk (25), severely depopulated (173), or extremely depopulated (523), as defined by Decree 108/2021 implementing Law February 2021 on depopulation. The sample is unevenly distributed, with the majority located in Cuenca (32.87 %) and Guadalajara (37.03 %), and fewer in Albacete (9.43 %), Ciudad Real (10.26 %), and Toledo (10.40 %).

3.2. Media ensemble database

Between January and May 2024, a mapping of media ensembles was carried out to identify local non-professional communication channels and information platforms in the 721 municipalities categorized as depopulated according to the Royal Decree 108/2021.

The database includes municipality, province, depopulation classification (risk, severe, or extreme), 2021 census population, population density, and contact number. Media ensemble components were coded as follows.

- Mobile Public Notice Apps (*Bando Móvil* and *Aymo*, the region’s most widespread).
- Messaging platforms (WhatsApp, Telegram), noting whether they are unidirectional or bidirectional.
- Official municipal Facebook pages.
- Municipal websites with updated local news.
- Non-professional media projects (community radio, newsletters, blogs, etc.).

The channels mapped derive from a prior observation of available resources that emerged during a mapping of professional media (Saiz-Echezarreta et al., 2023) and align with previous studies that have highlighted the relevance of networks such as Facebook and WhatsApp as tools used by municipalities to disseminate information (López Alonso & Moreno López, 2019). Moreover, in contrast to other social networks primarily used by people under 35—such as Instagram, X, or TikTok—Facebook (27 %) and WhatsApp (25 %) are more widespread among older age groups in Spain (Sierra et al., 2025, p. 74), who represent the majority of the population in the municipalities studied, characterized by demographic decline. The information-gathering procedure followed several strategies. First, the 721 municipalities were contacted by phone calls to their town councils collect information about their communication resources, with particular attention to confirming the use of WhatsApp and the existence of non-professional media, which may also include non-digitalized outlets (e.g., printed magazines). The availability of an updated news section on the websites of municipalities with an official portal was verified, the existence of a municipal Facebook page for each town was checked through online searches, and data on mobile applications were collected both through direct contact with one of the companies (*Aymo*), which provided the list of municipalities using its services, and by searching each municipality within the *Bando Móvil* application. The channels are strictly municipal in scope; they do not cover more than one municipality.

We use municipal communication channels as indicators of communication activity. Although alternative local sources exist, official channels are typically collective and authorized. Informal channels often lack clear authorship, raising methodological issues regarding their representativeness or potential to foster exclusion. This mapping strategy, while innovative, entails important limitations. First, it primarily captures digital and institutional communication channels. Informal communication practices (e.g., private WhatsApp groups, oral information flows, etc.) remain largely outside the scope of this database, despite their proven relevance in small-scale territories, and should require an ethnographic approach in each territory. Second, the offer of availability of media ensembles do not guarantee a full access, but this initial approach will help to highlight interesting landmarks for future case-studies. These limitations do not undermine the descriptive value of the database but suggest that future research should complement digital mapping with ethnographic or survey-based approaches to capture a fuller range of communicative practices.

Unlike previous studies (e.g., Saiz-Echezarreta et al., 2023), which aggregated data by depopulation zones, this study uses the municipality as the unit of analysis to highlight specific local dynamics potentially obscured by zone-level aggregation. Prior research (Ruiz Pulpón, 2024) suggests combining zonal diagnostics with disaggregated studies to better detect municipalities that deviate from general patterns. Identifying distinctive local behaviors is particularly useful for in-depth qualitative approaches such as ethnography.

Statistical analysis and data visualization were conducted using ArcGIS Pro 3.4.0 and SPSS 9.9.0.0, in three phases.

- a **Territorial Distribution of Media Ensemble Components.** Each component was treated as a binary variable for descriptive statistical analysis (mean, standard deviation), also analyzed by population size. The 721 municipalities were grouped into six population brackets. Most fall under 100 inhabitants (36.75 %) or between 101 and 500 (34.40 %). Maps were created to visualize distribution patterns.
- b **Relationship Between Media Ensembles and Other Factors.** Inferential analysis was conducted using multiple regression. A composite variable (0–5) was created by summing the number of media ensemble components, used as a proxy for municipal communication activity. We hypothesize that a higher number of channels increases not only activity but also diversity and connectivity, both locally and externally.

Several explanatory models were tested, treating the composite variable as the dependent variable. These models align with four sub-hypotheses, summarized in Table 1.

- *Sociodemographic Hypothesis*: Higher indicators of depopulation (aging, masculinization, low income, low immigration) correlate with lower communication activity.
- *Local Social Fabric Hypothesis*: A stronger associative, commercial, or tourism fabric correlates with larger media ensembles.
- *Traditional Media Hypothesis*: The presence of legacy media supports the growth of local digital/hyperlocal outlets, as shown by Negreir-a-Rey et al. (2023).
- *Geographic Hypothesis*: Population density, proximity to larger towns, and depopulation zoning affect the size of local media ensembles.

Most data were sourced from Castilla-La Mancha’s Open Data Portal, except average income (INE), the DESCOM media structure database (Saiz-Echezarreta et al., 2023), and travel time estimates, adapted from Ruiz-Pulpón and Martínez Sánchez-Mateos (2022).

Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated between the dependent and independent variables. Various linear regression models were tested. Although ordinal and multinomial regressions were initially considered, their results were unsatisfactory (significant parallelism test; low pseudo-R²). We opted to treat the media ensemble variable as continuous,² designing two models: an unweighted stepwise and a weighted least squares (WLS) model to correct potential heteroscedasticity. The stepwise model yielded an adjusted R² of 0.289, standard error of 1.004, and a Durbin-Watson score of 2.018, with residuals meeting the assumptions of normality, independence, and homoscedasticity.

c *Exploration of Geographic Patterns*. The geographic hypothesis was tested using ArcGIS Pro-3.4.0 tools. In the regression models, travel distance to urban centers did not significantly correlate with media ensemble size. Low R² values prompted a shift to a descriptive geographic approach to better understand differing communication activity levels among demographically similar but spatially distinct municipalities. Spatial regressions proved inconclusive, so we turned to map-based analysis to detect global (Hot Spot) and local (Cluster and Outlier) spatial correlations—methods currently prevalent in this type of analysis (Fatima et al., 2021).

Table 1
Indicators and sources.

Hypothesis	Indicators	Source
Sociodemographic	- Aging rate	Open Data Portal CLM
	- Masculinization ratio	Open Data Portal CLM
	- % of foreign population	Open Data Portal CLM
	- Average income	INE
	- Population	Open Data Portal CLM
Local Social Fabric	- Associations	Open Data Portal CLM
	- Restaurants per capita	Open Data Portal CLM
	- Hotel beds per capita	Open Data Portal CLM
Traditional Media	- Presence of legacy media	DESCOM Database. Own elaboration
Geographic	- Population density	Open Data Portal CLM
	- Rural Zoning (1, 2, 2.5)	Open Data Portal CLM
	- Travel time to nearest town >3000	Own elaboration

Source: own elaboration

4. Results

4.1. Territorial deployment of media ensemble components

4.1.1. Facebook

As previous studies have shown, local Facebook groups often serve the functions of a local newspaper in news deserts, providing news and hosting debates on local issues (Collier & Graham, 2022; Nygren et al., 2018). In Castilla-La Mancha, Facebook is the most widespread channel: 57 % of municipalities (411) have an official profile, with this figure exceeding 80 % in municipalities with more than 500 inhabitants (see Fig. 1). This high rate can be explained by the platform’s free access, its versatility for content publishing, and its 70 % penetration rate among the population (Periodismo 2030, 2022). These accounts act as digital notice boards, used not only to share upcoming municipal activities but also to inform about local issues such as street problems or interruptions in water or TV services. They often reference other networks like WhatsApp channels or groups as a way for residents to contact the municipality.

4.1.2. Direct messaging channels

Direct messaging apps—primarily WhatsApp³—are the most widely used communication tools among the population in Castilla-La Mancha, with only 9 % reporting never using them (Periodismo 2030, 2022). Yet, as a municipal communication channel, they are only used in 18.17 % of municipalities (n = 131). However, usage is notably higher in towns with 2000–5000 inhabitants (30.23 %) and in areas facing extreme depopulation. In these depopulated municipalities, 74 % of WhatsApp channels (n = 97) are found, of which 41 % (n = 55) are unidirectional and 32 % (n = 42) bidirectional (see Fig. 2). Notably, among the 51 bidirectional channels, 25 are in municipalities with fewer than 100 residents, and 21 in towns with 100–500 residents, suggesting that messaging apps are especially effective for municipal communication in very small localities.

4.1.3. Mobile Public Notice Apps

In addition to messaging apps, other tools have emerged in recent years to facilitate communication between local authorities and citizens. These are the digital version of traditional municipal edicts—mobile apps like *Bandomóvil* and *Aymo* that allow municipalities to send relevant public information (see Fig. 3). They are used in 36.2 % of depopulated municipalities (n = 261), with the highest adoption in medium-sized towns (1000–5000 inhabitants). However, these apps have two limitations: they are developed by private companies and thus incur costs, and they require a higher level of digital literacy compared to more common messaging tools.

4.1.4. News Sections on Municipal Websites

Another channel for municipal activity dissemination is the official website. Some of these portals include a news section, though updates are often irregular. Overall, 34.95 % of municipalities (n = 252) publish news on their websites (see Fig. 4). Again, this resource is more common in larger towns (over 1000 residents). In many small municipalities, there is no local website; instead, they use Spain’s national portal, <https://administracion.gob.es>, to provide basic information and contact details.

4.1.5. Informal local media projects

The DESCOM database collected both professional local media

³ Although they were coded under the same variable, the use of Telegram is very limited among the depopulated municipalities of Castilla-La Mancha. As noted in some telephone interviews, using Telegram would create more problems than solutions for an aging population that is more accustomed to WhatsApp.

Fig. 1. Municipalities with local Facebook Group.
Source: Own Elaboration.

Fig. 2. Municipalities with direct messaging channels.
Source: own elaboration.

outlets in Castilla-La Mancha (e.g., local press or conventional municipal radio) and smaller-scale communication initiatives. In this section, however, our focus is restricted to **informal communication projects** that are irregular and often led by local associations or by the municipalities themselves. These initiatives differ from professional outlets in that they lack stable funding and continuity, yet they remain relevant for community information flows. They were found in only 4.85 % of municipalities ($n = 35$) and are primarily cultural magazines often linked to local festivals, though some blogs, podcasts, and school-based online radio stations were also identified (see Fig. 5). Most are in towns with 1000–5000 residents. Although professional outlets could also be considered part of the broader media ensembles, in this case they are treated separately, since our multivariable analysis precisely aims to contrast the relationship between professional and non-professional resources.

In summary, as shown in Table 2, municipal Facebook profiles are the most common component in these areas, while other tools—such as mobile notice apps or website news sections—are more typical of medium-sized towns. In smaller and more depopulated municipalities, WhatsApp channels are the primary communication tool.

4.2. Media ensemble as an indicator of communication activity

While studying the adoption of media ensembles provides insight into each channel’s specificity, it does not fully explain the presence of highly active municipalities regardless of their population. A composite variable was created to sum the number of channels and communication projects per municipality (ranging from 0 to 5). This media ensemble score serves as an indicator of local communication activity.

Initial analysis shows that smaller towns tend to have lower

Fig. 3. Municipalities with mobile public notice apps.
Source: own elaboration.

Fig. 4. Municipalities with news sections on municipal websites.
Source: own elaboration.

ensemble scores, yet 14.3 % of towns with under 100 residents reached the maximum score of 5 (see Table 3).

4.2.1. Bivariate correlations

Pearson’s correlation confirms significant relationships between the dependent variable (media ensemble) and most defined indicators. Sociodemographic indicators show significant correlations ($p < 0.001$): aging rate ($r = -0.300$), masculinization ratio ($r = -0.293$), per capita income ($r = -0.416$), and population size ($r = 0.459$). Population size is the strongest predictor—larger towns tend to have higher ensemble scores. High aging rates, male-skewed populations, and higher incomes are associated with fewer channels. No significant correlation was found with the percentage of foreign-born population, likely due to uneven

Fig. 5. Municipalities with an active local media project. Source: own elaboration.

Table 2 Media ensemble component adoption by municipal population size (%).

Municipality size	Facebook	Messaging	Notice app	Web news	Local media
< 100	31,32 %	16,60 %	10,94 %	15,47 %	2,26 %
101–500	61,69 %	18,15 %	36,69 %	33,46 %	2,42 %
501–1000	80,23 %	16,28 %	67,44 %	44,18 %	2,33 %
1001–2000	82,09 %	19,40 %	71,64 %	71,64 %	14,93 %
2001–5000	90,70 %	30,23 %	65,11 %	76,74 %	23,26 %
> 5000	100,00 %	16,67 %	58,33 %	75 %	8,33 %
Total (n = 721)	57,00 %	18,17 %	36,2 %	34,95 %	4,85 %

Source: own elaboration

Table 3 Municipal population distribution by number of informal channels (%).

Population	Number of channels						Total
	0	1	2	3	4	5	
<100	73,8	40,9	21,4	8,2	3,2	14,3	36,2
101–500	26,2	42,5	43,8	30,9	16,1	0,0	35,6
501–1000	0,0	11,8	15,7	20,9	12,9	0,0	11,5
1001–2000	0,0	3,8	12,4	23,6	22,6	42,9	9,6
2001–5000	0,0	1,1	4,8	13,6	38,7	14,3	5,6
> 5000	0,0	0,0	1,9	2,7	6,5	28,6	1,5
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

Source: own elaboration

Table 4 Bivariate correlations with the dependent variable.

	Correlación de Pearson	Sig. (bilateral)
Sociodemographic indicator		
Aging rate	−0.300***	<0.001
Masculinization ratio	−0.293***	<0.001
% foreign-born population	0.052	0.081
Per capita income	−0.416***	<0.001
Population size	0.459***	<0.001
Local Social Fabric indicator		
Associations per capita	−0.339***	<0.001
Restaurants per capita	−,101**	,003
Hotel beds per capita	−,089**	,009
Media indicator		
Presence of conventional media	0.247***	<0.001
Geographic indicator		
Population density	0.091**	0.008
Rural Zoning (1, 2, 2.5)	0.244***	<0.001
Average travel time to town >3000 people	−0.158***	<0.001

* Significant at $p < 0.05$; ** Significant at $p < 0.01$; * Significant at $p < 0.001$. Source: own elaboration

distribution across similarly structured municipalities (see Table 4).⁴

The local social fabric hypothesis does not appear to hold as expected, since a higher number of registered associations per inhabitant correlates negatively ($r = -0.339$) with a higher number of municipal

⁴ The proportion of foreign population in the depopulated areas of Castilla-La Mancha varies widely, ranging from below 1 % in 76 municipalities to over half in places like Heras de Ayuso or Torre del Burgo. Similar contrasts can be found between nearby, comparable municipalities: for instance, Mirabueno (Guadalajara) has 78 inhabitants and not a single foreign resident, whereas neighboring Algora, with 82 inhabitants, has a migration rate of 26 %. Areas categorized as facing extreme or severe depopulation concentrate the highest percentages of foreign population in some provinces (Guadalajara-2: 16.73 % and Cuenca-5: 16.73 %) and the lowest in others (Albacete-6: 3.24 % and Ciudad Real-8: 2.27 %).

channels. This could tentatively be explained by assuming that in municipalities with more associations per inhabitant, communication needs may be met through the associations themselves rather than through the channels studied as media ensembles, which are more generalist. With a lower level of significance ($p < 0.01$), a negative correlation is also observed between the degree of media ensemble and the number of hospitality establishments per inhabitant ($r = -0.101$), on the one hand, and with the number of hotel beds per inhabitant ($r = -0.089$), on the other. Although both may suggest a potential negative relationship between the hospitality sector as a whole (tourism indicators) and media dynamism, the lower significance of the test and the particularly low coefficients prevent drawing firm conclusions on this point.

The media hypothesis, based on a single indicator, does point to a moderate relationship ($r = 0.247$) between the existence of conventional media and greater dynamism in the municipality's media ensemble. The geographical hypothesis, however, yields less reliable results. First, population density does correlate positively with a higher number of channels, as might be expected. However, a lower level of significance ($p < 0.01$) and a particularly weak coefficient ($r = 0.091$) qualify the result considerably. This is due, among other factors, to the disproportion in some municipalities between their total area in square kilometers and the extent of their inhabited area—for instance, Almodóvar del Campo, with just over five thousand registered inhabitants and an area of 1208 km². The zoning levels do seem to clearly indicate ($r = 0.244$; $p < 0.001$) a higher development of media ensembles in municipalities at risk of depopulation than in those facing more extreme situations, although this is an indicator with a high probability of collinearity with population size. Finally, travel time shows a weak negative correlation ($r = -0.158$; $p < 0.001$), which could suggest that municipalities farther from more populated centers in the region are less likely to be media-dynamic—that is, to have a higher number of channels.

4.2.2. Multiple linear regression models

As shown in Table 5, the stepwise model selected three indicators as significant predictors: Municipal population ($\beta = 0.326$, $p < 0.001$), Average income per inhabitant ($\beta = -0.223$, $p < 0.001$), and Associations per inhabitant ($\beta = -0.148$, $p < 0.001$), thereby confirming that the local social fabric hypothesis is demonstrated in the opposite direction to what was theoretically expected (i.e., the fewer associations per inhabitant, the higher the score in the media ensemble), and that the sociodemographic hypothesis can be partially confirmed, at least in relation to population size and income level, pointing to a more developed media ensemble in more populated municipalities with lower income levels. Since the VIFs (Variance Inflation Factors, which quantify the intensity of multicollinearity in regressions) are well below the maximum threshold of 10, it can be asserted that there are no multicollinearity problems among the selected variables.

The weighted least squares (WLS, Table 6) stepwise model yields an adjusted R² of 0.137, having been weighted based on the population of the municipality as the variable with the greatest explanatory power in the previous model. With a Durbin-Watson test result of 1.980 and an effective correction for heteroscedasticity, the model maintains the significance and the variables of the previous model with VIF below 1.3 but presents a moderately high dispersion of the residuals, which may indicate that some observations disproportionately affect the model.

The results of the regression models moderately confirm the first two

Table 5 Stepwise regression model (unweighted).

	B	SE	β	t	p	VIF
Constant	3100	,263		11,772	<,001	
Population	,000	,000	,326	9345	<,001	1221
Per capita income	,000	,000	-,223	-6054	<,001	1357
Associations per capita	-2897	,692	-,148	-4189	<,001	1250

Source: own elaboration

Table 6 Stepwise regression model (WLS).

	B	SE	β	t	p	VIF
Constant	2263	,348		6508	<,001	
Population	,001	,000	,230	5963	<,001	1228
Per capita income	,000	,000	-,166	-4332	<,001	1215
Associations per capita	-,872	,285	-,109	-3060	,002	1059

Source: own elaboration

sub-hypotheses, while confirming nothing about the media and geographic hypotheses. Assuming that the non-significance of the media hypothesis indicator may be due to collinearity with population size, the question remains as to the relevance of geographic factors on the size of the municipal ensemble mean. To clarify this last question, we have proceeded with the ArcGIS-assisted geographic analysis described below.

4.2.3. Spatial pattern exploration

In the multiple regression models, the indicator of distance by transport to urban centers did not correlate with the size of the media ensembles and, consequently, with greater or lesser media activity. This, added to very low R² values in both models, led us to test a geographic approach to better understand the unequal communication activity in municipalities with similar sociodemographic conditions but different locations. After testing a Geographically Weight Regression (GWR) with the previous indicators without significant results in practically any town, we opted for a more descriptive approach to the empirical evidence, drawing a strategy of mappings of the dependent variable reinforced by a Hot Spots analysis and another of Clusters and Outliers based on Moran's I.

Fig. 6 shows the distribution of the media ensemble variable across the municipalities. The first noticeable aspect is the clear difference between the two macro-areas of depopulation: in the northeastern area, which includes most of the provinces of Guadalajara and Cuenca and part of Albacete, the presence of municipalities with no communication channels is significantly higher than in the southwestern area (which includes parts of Toledo, Ciudad Real, and Albacete), whereas the presence of what could be termed super-communicators (villages in a situation of depopulation with four or more channels) is more common in the latter than in the former. However, the distribution of these super-communicators is uneven: 34.21 % are in Ciudad Real, Cuenca and Guadalajara each have 21.05 %, Albacete accounts for 13.16 %, and Toledo the remaining 10.53 %, again with no clear sociodemographic patterns.

The only discernible pattern at this level is an apparent local concentration of municipalities with a high number of informal channels. To confirm this assertion, the study's dependent variable was subjected to two successive analyses: a Hot Spots analysis, aimed at globally detecting areas with highly or weakly clustered patterns, and a Clusters & Outliers analysis, which, using Moran's I, identifies patterns of local spatial autocorrelation. The results can be seen in Figs. 7 and 8.

The Hot Spots distribution clearly confirms the spatial patterns initially observed: in the south of the Autonomous Community, there are several hot spots where municipalities with a high media ensemble are concentrated, while cold spots are distributed in the north, particularly in the provinces of Guadalajara and Cuenca. The Clusters & Outliers analysis, for its part, shows—with a z-score of 15.78—that there are clustered patterns of the variable with a 99.99 % confidence level. Fig. 7 shows that there are at least three areas with a high concentration pattern of media ensembles: the first spans from the northwest of Ciudad Real to the south of Toledo; the second, from the southeast of Ciudad Real to the entire western area of Albacete; and the third extends from the southwest of Cuenca to the east of Albacete.

What does this pattern of concentration of municipalities with a high media ensemble in various areas of the region suggest? A previously

Fig. 6. Distribution of *media ensemble*.
Source: own elaboration.

Fig. 7. Hot spots analysis.
Source: own elaboration.

unconsidered version of the geographic hypothesis seems to emerge from these findings: municipalities with a dynamic media ensemble—regardless of population size or other factors—tend to be located near other municipalities with an above-average media ensemble. In other words, it could exist a local contagion effect in the use of informal communication channels such as WhatsApp groups, Facebook pages, or local news websites, a kind of municipal inspiration stemming from neighboring municipalities that take innovative communication initiatives in their area, whether these are official projects or social media channels. This would be consistent with the existing literature on the subject, which points to a tendency toward spatial dependence among neighboring municipalities (Qin, 2024).

Although it should be interpreted with caution, the suggestion of a possible “contagion effect” or mutual inspiration among neighboring

municipalities remains a plausible hypothesis. The current data do not allow us to definitively establish mechanisms of diffusion or influence between municipalities. Therefore, we propose this as an emerging line of inquiry for future research, which could explore these dynamics through qualitative approaches or longitudinal designs that trace the development and adoption of communication practices over time.

5. Discussion and conclusions

This research aimed to deepen the understanding of media ensembles in depopulated rural municipalities broadly categorized as news deserts, within the framework of the mediatization paradigm. Firstly, the findings confirm the existence of characteristic patterns in the media ensembles of these areas (Objective 1). The data show that despite the

Fig. 8. Clusters and outliers analysis.
Source: own elaboration.

scarcity of professional media—only 17 outlets were registered in DESCOM in 2023 across the 721 municipalities under study—other communication channels persist, reinforcing the idea of communicative resilience (Usher, 2021). In line with previous studies (Collier & Graham, 2022; Nygren et al., 2018), the results reveal that Facebook is the predominant tool among those mapped in these municipalities, although in the least populated ones, direct messaging tools such as WhatsApp are more frequently used. These differences, among others, highlight the importance of further exploring the adaptability of media ensembles in relation to sociodemographic and geographic characteristics.

Our regression models yielded modest R^2 values—0.289 in the stepwise model and 0.137 in the weighted least squares model—which is not uncommon in social science research addressing complex phenomena such as local communication dynamics (Cohen et al., 2003; Gelman & Hill, 2007). Regarding the analysis of sociodemographic variables and their relationship with the media ensemble, bivariate analysis showed only partial correlations, and our multiple regression identified merely three significant predictors—municipal population, average income per capita, and associations per capita—with limited explanatory power (Objective 2). These low R^2 values suggest that a substantial portion of the variability in media ensemble activity is driven by a multitude of unobserved factors intrinsic to depopulated municipalities, including specific contextual, demographic, and socioeconomic conditions, as well as other influences that were not captured in our model. Furthermore, similar studies in rural communications and social geography have reported comparable levels of explanatory power (Collier & Graham, 2022; Gulyás, Jenkins, & Bergström, 2023), reinforcing the notion that—even with limited variance explained—the statistically significant predictors and overall model diagnostics still offer valuable insights into the patterns of municipal communication practices.

To overcome these limitations in the statistical analysis, an alternative approach using geographic analysis tools was proposed, which revealed more significant findings both at a general level (Hot Spots analysis) and a local level (Cluster and Outlier analysis). A clear divide was identified between the north and south of the region in terms of

spatial concentration of municipalities with dense media ensembles. In particular, the northern provinces (Guadalajara, Toledo, and Cuenca) are significantly less dynamic than the southern ones (Ciudad Real and Albacete), suggesting a strong geographic influence on communication practices, which also relates to the average population size of municipalities in each area. Since some areas of the region are characterized by a high number of municipalities with very small populations, it is necessary to explore how public administrations might provide information services beyond municipal boundaries, for instance, through county-based or inter-municipal models, an adaptation already being explored in the provision of other municipal services (Santiago Iglesias & De Nuccio, 2023).

At the same time, geographic analysis made it possible to confirm and visualize an unforeseen trend: the mutual influence between neighboring municipalities, which seems to play a key role in the development of communication channels. A concentration of media-dynamic municipalities with rich media ensembles can be observed, suggesting patterns of spatial dependency and the diffusion of communication practices (Qin, 2024). These findings support the need to integrate geographic analysis with the study of media ensembles (Objective 3), as this combined perspective enables a better understanding of communicative activity patterns rooted in territorial contexts.

Moreover, the results revealed the existence of singular municipalities—not necessarily large in population—that show stronger communicative resilience. It is important to understand the role of these municipalities and the direction and mechanisms through which influence is exerted between them. Therefore, a future line of inquiry will involve case studies in the areas identified as highly communicatively dynamic in the Hot Spot and Cluster analyses. This includes a deeper investigation into rural social innovation processes within the media-tization paradigm to explore practices emerging from communities that capitalize on the opportunities of digitalization (Zerrer et al., 2022), and to advance the understanding of rural mediatization processes in comparison to urban ones (Zerrer, 2024).

Concerning the fieldwork, the Media Ensembles database complements previous censuses of professional media (DESCOM) and

contributes to a better understanding of communication in depopulated areas. Interestingly, through informants, we identified communication projects that could be considered alternative and which would be overlooked from a more conventional approach to local media—such as annual magazines produced for local festivals. These resources, with varying degrees of professionalization, may offer new avenues for research by serving as indicators of communicative resilience in rural settings where practices are tailored to local needs and do not always conform to traditional commercial media models. Their inclusion as a variable also represents an innovative approach to the study of rural communication.

These communicative ecosystems in news deserts pose new challenges: the withdrawal of local journalism and its replacement by institutionally mediated forms of communication may not fully fulfill the traditional functions of journalism, potentially limiting the plurality of perspectives and constraining the capacity for oversight and critique of local power. From another perspective, however, the global and delocalized nature of some of these digital channels (e.g., Facebook pages) can strengthen emotional bonds and maintain contact among people who live far away but wish to stay connected to their roots, thereby achieving one of the purposes of local communication (López García, 2004).

Several limitations of this study should be acknowledged. As an exploratory study, we accept the results of the statistical models with adjusted R^2 values in order to design new hypothesis to conform better models. Although multiple regression techniques were tested, including alternative ordinal and multinomial models, the composite media ensemble variable was ultimately treated as continuous to facilitate analysis. We recognize that this decision introduces limitations, as the variable represents a count of components rather than a truly continuous measure. The findings should therefore be interpreted with caution and viewed primarily as an initial approximation aimed at identifying potential patterns and generating hypotheses for future research. Further studies incorporating additional qualitative dimensions and longitudinal data will be essential to strengthen the explanatory robustness and to capture the complex interplay of sociopolitical, historical, and contextual factors or other still unexplored elements of the local media ecosystem—such as those linked to broader digitalization processes like the Smart Rural Territory Strategy (<https://territorioruralinteligente.castillalamancha.es/>), that shape local communicative dynamics in depopulated rural areas.

Another issue is the lack of official and up-to-date censuses of local media in Spain, both professional and community-based, which necessitates the creation of ad hoc datasets and limits the ability to conduct regional or national comparative studies. Additionally, as this study represents an initial phase of inquiry, it focused on the availability of channels without delving into the quality of the content or how these resources are used by local citizens.

Despite these limitations, the approach presented here also contributes several relevant theoretical and methodological insights for the design of future research. First, the concept of media ensembles offers a useful theoretical lens to understand communicative resilience in depopulated contexts. This approach allows us to move beyond the negative narrative of news deserts and instead focus on the local processes that sustain communicative dynamics, avoiding a restrictive view limited to the traditional commercial media model.

Second, media ensembles are dynamic processes in constant adaptation, requiring both historical interpretation and future-oriented projection. This can be developed through the design and maintenance of updated databases. A longitudinal approach deployed over successive phases will help deepen the understanding of the links between media logics and territorial identity and cohesion, generating new evidence to determine whether the presence of media that register municipal activity and everyday life has an impact on local social networks and community-building, as well as on connections with surrounding territories.

Third, as a general framework, it enables scalar analysis (Hepp, 2025), allowing the methodological design presented here to be combined with other approaches. These could explore, for instance, the subjective perspective of local actors on media ensembles and how they incorporate them through individual media repertoires (Poztel et al., 2024)—that is, how people use available channels and integrate them into their everyday information practices regarding the local or regional context. Another avenue would be to study how a community, as a constellation of specific actants, interprets, legitimizes, appropriates, creates, transforms, or discontinues available information channels (Hasebrink, Merten & Behre, 2023), and to what extent political actions and various contextual conditions influence the implementation and diffusion of the infrastructures, resources, and practices that make up each media ensemble.

Finally, in terms of contributions to the demographic challenge, this study shows that while the diagnosis of depopulation has been widely addressed by other disciplines and is largely consolidated, its connection with communication remains underexplored. This research underscores the need to develop methods and approaches that guide the design and implementation of public communication initiatives, measures, and policies in rural territories, especially those with low population density. All these proposals call for deeper development of methodologies that allow for quantitative diagnostics while also pointing the way toward qualitative fieldwork at the local level in the most relevant areas.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Francisco Javier Rueda-Córdoba: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Vanesa Sáiz-Echezarreta:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Belén Galletero-Campos:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Declaration of the use of AI assisted technologies

During the preparation of this work the authors used AI assisted technologies for proof reading and spell checking. The authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Ethical statement

The authors declare that ethical approval is not applicable to this manuscript.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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